

Gender Equality and Women Economic Empowerment: An Analysis of ZAOGA FIF Church in Masvingo, Zimbabwe

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ABSTRACT

Despite fact that gender equality and socio-economic position of women continues impugned in religious companionship, this research ascertains that Faith Based Institutions have been auxiliary in addressing gender inequality and economic disempowerment of women in Zimbabwe. To that note, ZAOGA FIF has consolidated gender equality through ordaining women as deacons; elders; pastors; bishops; evangelists and overseers. Through talents, women are entrusted to execute both formal and informal businesses from a religious background. Equally important, these talents have accomplished and provoked the consciousness of women capabilities. Mammoth scholarship by Professor E.H Gutu (Church founder) provided much needed secondary data. Purposive sampling was employed to acquire information from five key informants from church leadership in Masvingo's five districts. Findings indicate that ZAOGA FIF's doctrine and practice of working using own hands among both sexes is not just a biblical debrief, but has advanced much towards poverty extermination in church and communities. This article accedes that women economic empowerment issues should be understood after comprehending historical development of talents.

Keywords: Gender Equality, Economic Women Empowerment, Faith Based institutions, Talents, tin-savings, Sexuality.

INTRODUCTION

This paper is a captious anatomisation of the belief or notion that gender is exclusively an academic authority allegorised with women. In gratifying that, the article appraises on how other Faith Based Institutions have condensed or curtailed development projects among both men and women. In the

backdrop of this paper, the Zimbabwe Assemblies of God Forward in Faith Ministries (ZAOGA FIF) spontaneously redesigned its responsibility towards the antecedently known culture of only economically empowering women through the accomplishment of talents; dress-making courses and tin-savings initiatives. Henceforward, envisaging the economic environment preponderating in Zimbabwe, the ZAOGA FIF through the leadership of its Archbishop, Professor E.H Gutu, has plumped gender equality projects and programs. For example, both men and women are unceasingly endowed with entrepreneurship dexterity or expertise (Shumba 2015). During the journey of this study, the researcher came to the conclusion that ZAOGA FIF, has applauded and emulated best gender equality practices as the various skills which are taught in their church are not selective in any way especially with particular focus on sexuality.

As one of the comprehensively acknowledged definitions, gender refers to how men and women are socialized in a particular society (Giddens, 2022). In some cases, the fashion or etiquette in which men and women are socialized is chiefly dependent on the various forces of socialization and churches like any other institutions represent these major forces of socialization (Haralambos & Holborn 2022). During my various intercommunication or synergy with both the senior and junior members of ZAOGA FIF, men and women and also through some surveillance, I observed that, in a varying circumstances, the Zimbabwean society and other societies from beyond the borders have got a serious misapprehension or hallucinations of *gender equality*, *talents; tin-savings* and *women economic empowerment*. For precedent, most of these people envision that *talents and tin banking* or savings are mainly done by women, and, men are not part and parcel of these socio- economic empowerment projects and programmes. Indisputably, this used to be the case, contemplating that long back in the history of ZAOGA FIF, more women were not formerly employed as compared to men, forthwith and fascinating to note is, Zimbabwe's unceremonious sector is galvanised by a greater portion of women than men (Magunje 2020). In extrapolating Gender Equality and Women Economic Emancipation, the paper concisely applied the Gender and Development Approach (GAD). This was vindicated because the approach recognises that development should be across-the-board irregardless of sex (Moser 2021). The fact that the GAD approach entraps the various magnitudes of development was another vital reason of using it as the visionary base of analysis. Still on the conceptual framework, the article has also engaged the Empowerment Framework approach advanced by Sara Longwe and Clarke (2022) as an investigative gadget or instrument to deconstruct the perspective of the church with regard to the socio-economic empowerment of women and girls. In addition to that, ZAOGA FIF, as a socialisation force has actually disentangled the societal culture of discriminating women on sexual grounds, but has further involved males within development processes, Charamba (2015).

In the procedure, men, being part and parcel of marriages as institutions and the church, are frequently involved in businesses with their women as a way of comprehending and endowing

or chartering the teachings of the Archbishop, Professor E.H Guti (Shumba 2015), Notably, this paper sanctioned the general belief of attributing gender with women as denoted by the admittance of both sexes in small to large businesses. Eventually, this has brought about the amelioration or advancement of the socio-economic status of both men and women within and outside the church.

BRIEF HISTORY OF ZAOGA FIF AND WOMEN ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT

It could be judicious to start by concurring that ZAOGA FIF has apparently developed from flange to extremity as mirrored by its enormous ballooning following. Commencing from a chagrined milieu, the Archbishop of ZAOGA FIF critiqued or examined the way he was taught or enlightened by God to 'Fear not, Sin not', (Muyambo and Machingura 2014). According to Guti, (2016) the divulgence started way back in the bushes of Ngaone in Chipinge District. Being one of the Faith Based Institution, the church has already been a fore-runner in teaching devotees the essentialities of working utilising their hands (Researchers' own observation). As a temperament or persona who endures irrefutable attestation to the fruition of working diligently from a modest root, Professor E.H Guti considers in the tutoring of *working talents and tin-savings* as a maintainable patent medicine of annihilating hardships and at least augment or escalate the livelihoods standards of persons (Guti 2016). It is also prudent to spotlight or stress this, with regard to the elucidation of women economic empowerment by ZAOGA FIF, the notion is not circumscribed to the *working of talents and tin-savings* in the context of the church itself, but there are some varied pathways and arbitrations which are used to economically empower women.

Guti (2015) reiterated that *talents and tin-savings* "is not an ideology designed by the church to get money from its congregants, but the church fortifying the believers on how they themselves can have money and come out of poverty". The establishment of more than 100 Dressmaking and Designing Schools by the ZAOGA FIF seems to have been targeted at women in order to gain skills and ultimately to become financially secure, (Tarugarira and Moyo, 2017). The ultimate belief by the church leadership is that empowerment must lead to a change which is to the advantage of the poor, the disadvantaged, and the marginalized. To that effect, the African Christian Business Fellowship (ACBF), as a church commenced formation, is embedded on the impression of nurturing populace on how to proficiently start their enterprises from scratch. The ACBF acknowledges affiliates to form alliances or synergies and in some specific situations seek spiritual mediator-ship in their various existences (Shumba 2015).

Most women economic empowerment coupled events began to outstretch after Ezekiel Guti, the church founder was free willed money and a fleet of buses by one white man in the United Kingdom to be under his stewardship. After consulting God, on whether to transact with the white man, Ezekiel was instructed to go back to Africa-Zimbabwe and teach people how to work using their hands (Musoni 2016). This has indeed enabled ZOAGA FIF through working *talents and tin-savings* to give birth to the construction of state of art churches, schools, orphanage centres,

hospitals and now the Zimbabwe Ezekiel Guti University (ZEGU) across the country, (Guti 2016). Furthermore, the mystically dexterous man constantly teaches congregants to commence businesses from a modest standing point. Initially, *talents and tin-banking* were principally administered by the females attributable to the tyrannical nature of the pre-independence Zimbabwe and this has seen many women who once used to be paltry housekeeper becoming conspicuous business persons (Musoni 2016). With an increased situation of developing and strengthening the skills (capacity building) from the church backing through *talents and tin-savings*, this write-up advances that ZAOGA FIF women have compelled to expunge poverty thereby improving their families' standard of living.

Defining Gender Equality and Women Economic Empowerment

Gender Equality

Gender equivalence and women empowerment are astronomically conceded as human rights that exist at the heart of development processes, UNDP (2019). They both work to conquer the barricade of stereotypes and prejudices so that both men and women are able to equitably devote to and benefit from economic, social, cultural and political developments amidst a given community. "Gender is seen as the process by which individuals who are born into biological categories of male or female become the social categories of men and women through the acquisition of locally-defined attributes of masculinity and femininity" (Kabeer 1991:11). According to Bawa, (2017) gender equality may be understood in three dimensions; (i) equality in access to and opportunities in economic, political, social and other fields, (ii) equality before and under the law and (iii) equality in dignity (internal worth) between men and women. Gender equality on the other hand entails leveling the playing field (that is, social, political, economic, cultural and religious) so that every person regardless of who they are and where they live has equal opportunity to grow and develop or showcase their potential, UN (2019).

Women Economic Empowerment

For ambitions of this write up, women economic empowerment should be understandably traced back to the emergence of various approaches to development process. It is therefore apropos to stretch out that as early as 1970s, the various researchers on development began to focus on the gendered division of labour and the impact of development and modernization strategies on women. Emphatically, it should be made clear that this approach to development came into use during the United Nations Decade for women between 1975 and 1985. This approach was uncelebrated due its conclusions that women were passive beneficiaries of development (Moyoyeta, 2022). The approach maintained how women were being left out of economic development and were significantly not benefiting from economic processes of change and development. With the passage of time, Gender and Development (GAD) approach emerged in the 1980's. As a contemporaneous procedure to development, its main tenet is to remove

discrepancies in economic equality between men and women (Moser 2021). In addition, what makes this methodology exceptional and indeed the best explanation of women economic empowerment is the fact that it deconstructs the idea of associating gender with women but rather accentuates that both men and women should be equally involved in development processes and procedures. From this perspective, the definitions of women economic empowerment in the following sections clearly parade how the comprehending of gender and development acknowledges socio-economic empowerment of women. This is also intermittently elongated in view of the endless contribution of men in the awakening of women economic empowerment.

Firstly, empowerment, as a broad term, applying to both men and women, can be understood as increasing the economic capabilities and economic standing points of individuals and communities (Musoni, 2020). This definition therefore entails that when individuals' capabilities are enhanced and essentialised, they are economically empowered. Contextually, increased economic strength of women eventually results in women's economic empowerment. Benefits associated include among others; increased economic productivity, higher family incomes, delayed marriages, reduced fertility rates and improved health and survival rates for infants and children, (UNFPA, 2016). To this end, the choices may be those related to education, participation, mobility, fertility, economic independence, political participation, employment, awareness and exercising of rights in all spheres of life. I therefore acknowledges that Faith Based Institutions directly and indirectly influence the socio-economic empowerment of women. The 'how is this achieved' is the reason behind conducting this study.

Secondly, Shumba (2015) deliberates that Women's Economic Empowerment should be understood as a transformational process associated with a sharp increase in the access to and control over economic entitlements and economic decisions. Although, many people from across the globe, tend to believe that Third world nations are characterised by the dominance of men in the economic fraternity and Zimbabwe include. Such an assertion is no-longer relevant in these nations due to overwhelming contribution brought about by various Faith Based Institutions particularly the Pentecostal denominations which are spreading like veld fire. This study, however, went an extra mile through qualifying and quantifying how Zimbabwean women, under the administration Archbishop Professor E.H Guti, have been involved in socio-economic development projects in both private and public spectrums. In accomplishing this, one of the encircling questions answered in this paper was; is the ZAOGA FIF founded on patriarchal systems especially considering members' economic empowerment? All being said, it is habitually acceded that where there is equal distribution of resources and women are in a position to own the means of production, women are therefore considered economically empowered.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section briefly disentangles the research design, research population and sample size, sampling techniques, data collection methods and data analysis procedures which were utilised in the research.

Research population and Sample size

Both women and men who confirm their membership by any means with ZAOGA FIF resemble target population in this particular research, especially those who resides in Masvingo either temporarily or permanently. As an individual who have both vast experience and acquainted milieu of the record of ZAOGA FIF, a few affiliates of the church management such as elders and pastors also contributed with functional information.

Sampling Techniques

ZAOGA FIF is based in forty three (43) provinces in Zimbabwe. Nevertheless, it is vital to note that these provinces are not the ones which are traditionally understood in geographic terms of the country but preferably they are the morphology of the church leadership due to its alarming growth. Subsequently, for impetus of this research, particular focus will be on Masvingo Province which consists of five districts, both Urban and Rural churches. This research made use of judgemental sampling to get five respondents among women and men from these provinces. The same sampling technique was also used to gather information from members of the church leadership such as church elders and pastors. The researcher believed that these selected people do have informed background on the history and strategic vision of ZAOGA FIF.

Data collection

Interviews and observations were instruments used to collect primary data while secondary data was collected through documentary review such as the scholarly articles provided by the Archbishop of ZAOGA FIF, Professor Guti.

Data Analysis and interpretation

Some conclusions based on the information acquired were used in interpreting and analysing the data. This means that the researcher made use of interpretivism.

RESULTS PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

ZAOGA FIF and Gender Equality

ZAOGA FIF as one of the Faith Based Institution in the province has played a decisive role in leveling the playing field by affording equal opportunities to both women and men in their church. The church's doctrine calls for equality among its members irregardless of sexuality. This stance has since allowed women to participate in high level authoritative position in the church and also take up influential positions in the public spectrum. From the researcher's observation, women in ZAOGA FIF are accredited as deacons; elders; pastors; evangelists; overseers and bishops. Women in this church are allowed to preach on the pulpit; act as marriage officers and also to lead funeral sessions. This is totally opposite to other African Initiated Churches where women are languishing in silence and treated as objects rather than subjects. One of the key informant has this to say:

Following the teachings from the co-founder and president of ZAOGA FIF, Doctor Eunor Guti, through ordination of women as pastors; evangelists; bishops; overseers; deacons and elders as well as giving them free and equal roles and responsibilities in the church, the status of gender equality have remarkably changed for better not only in the church but also in the society in general, (10/11/21).

Another key informant has this to say:

The ZAOGA FIF Church is promoting the inculturation of Christianity by interpreting the Gospel message in a new perception that is both liberating and empowering especially to their female colleagues and followers. Not only have they managed to break cultural barricades engendered in the patriarchal culture, but they are also agents of change, for they have contributed to the evolution of a new concept of church which is more inclusive and recognizes the varied talents and insights of both men and women in the church and society at large, (10/11/21).

The researcher confirmed that, while religion has been a powerful source for the subservience of women in society, however contrary to ZAOGA FIF Church's teachings and practices, it has turned out to be an important universal source for the feminist movement and other social and political movements for human liberalism. This is particularly evident in that the church has provided women with opportunities for leadership, education, and the development of organizational dexterities, a rare scenario in other African Initiated Churches (AICs) in the province, (Researcher's observation).

ZAOGA FIF and Women Economic Empowerment

As alluded earlier on, men and women of ZAOGA FIF community are economically empowered through the work of talents and tin-banking. However, important results obtained in this research indicate that people are not always compelled or contrived to dwell on working talents and do tin-banking but rather, they are also involved in some business fellowship with business people of a high standing. For instance, this has been immanenced by the African Christian Business Fellowship, which is a church initiative decreed to train not only members of the church but also individuals from outside the church. All the key informants of this research confidently established that, ZAOGA FIF as a faith based institution, has not only instituted massive strides towards the economic empowerment of women but has also recorded a path of serious learning as women themselves confirmed that they are experiencing positive growth especially in the economic fraternity.

It is pertinent to note from the onset that, as a means of economically empowering church members, talents and tin-banking were initially meant to economically empower women. It was further indicated that talents and tin-banking were regarded as women only for the sole purpose of maintaining the tradition of the church. One of the key respondents indicated that;

The fact that women constituted a greater percentage of the ZAOGA FIF population, there was need to specifically focus on this sex. However, with a change in the condition of the Zimbabwean economy and the demographic makeup of ZAOGA FIF beginning as early as 2000 there was need to include men in the work of talents. To make contents worse, some of the men started losing jobs. This analytically justifies why these talents and tin-banking are now being understood as for the family and not for women.

The above assertions are indeed true manifestation of how development projects and initiatives should be broad-spectrum and dovetail equity issues. The study also established that the fact that men are also affected by some economic problems, it will not make sense to sideline them in development processes. As can be understood from the above testimony, men also experience barriers in some aspects of development hence the need for all-embracing approaches and partnerships to scale up women's economic empowerment. Further, it seems there is problem of thinking that women are the only people involved in low-value added occupations that generate little economic returns.

Women Economic Empowerment in Masvingo's Remote Areas

Proving the point on how the church is resolute in bettering the sustenance or livelihood status of its people irregardless of geographical standings and sexuality stances, the church's alcove or calling even reach out to the negligible areas of Masvingo province such as Mwenezi, Maranda, Chikombedzi and Checheche. It should also be made undoubtedly clear that most of these areas

are poverty afflicted and limited in socio-economic growth. Though engulfed in poverty stricken situation, these communities have been trained and acknowledged the tutoring of working tin-banking and talents. To showcase the achievement of working tin-banking and talents, women in lower Mwenezi started talents by harvesting *madora* from Mopani forests and selling them. To that effect, one of the respondents (*interviewed, 27 November 2021*) had this to say;

These women have even gained huge profits from selling Madora. Further, whilst the selling of madora has largely been affiliated with the gender concept of femininity in Zimbabwe, men are also been involved in such small scale businesses. Such has been obligated by the befitting teachings of Archbishop, Professor EH Guti who constantly emphasises that both men and women should at least participate in small businesses so that they sustain themselves in the current Zimbabwean economic austerity.

In view of the above sentiments, this research is therefore intrinsically coerced to appreciate the vibrant responsibility and command of women in the socio-economic processes of ZAOGA FIF and Zimbabwe at large. In addition, to showcase how the gender equality territory has redesigned its attention in the socialization process, the involvement of men in the selling of *madora* is indeed a convincing evidence.

Furthermore, as has been insinuated to earlier on, the calling of ZAOGA FIF also reach out to accommodate those secluded places such as Chikombedzi which shares border with Mozambique. It is debated that, taking advantage of their closeness to Mozambique, these women and men get second hand goods from Mozambique at a cheaper price and sell them in Zimbabwe at a higher price so as to maximise the profits, (Manganga 2017). It is therefore worth noting that, history unveiled above indeed showcase on how the economic continuance of ZAOGA FIF should be understood from a modest background. Due to success stories displayed by *tin-savings and working talents*, most women started to apprehend their full potential in both private and public spheres. The various magnitudes of socio-economic empowerment of women will be critically diagnosed from a gendered point of view in the following section. This is more justifiable because most of these activities have directly and indirectly posed a notable bearing on men.

Talents and Tin-Banking: Supplements to Husband Earnings

Indications alluded from the previous sections shows that in ZAOGA FIF, more men are generally involved in formal employment and at the other end a greater portion of women are also engaged in formal employment. Due to catastrophic economic situation peddling the country, women become more involved in small, medium and even large businesses, as a way to augment the monthly earnings of their husbands. It was argued that women empowerment itself should not be restricted to individual growth and capabilities but also the ability of an individual to compliment and raise the livelihoods status of a family as an institution. One of the respondents has this to say;

The fact that women are selling from as little as sweets and chocolates, economically means that there are returns to the family whether financial or non-financial. Also, the clear fact of the matter is that when a wife is engaging in small or even large businesses she becomes less dependent on the husband and the husband will directly or indirectly appreciate the ownership and control of some resources by the wife. Obviously, when that happens, dependence is demystified and a woman becomes economically empowered.

A closer judgement from the above statement would imply that when a woman is economically beneficial, she is not only remarkable to her husband but also to the family at large. As such, one can conclude that socio-economic empowerment also reach out to imply a progression in the determination of the channelization of resources impartially at family level.

ZAOGA FIF'S Stance on Financial Management and Women Economic Empowerment

ZAOGA FIF through its leadership has clearly demonstrated that they provide tutorials and refresher lessons to its congregants and outsiders on both financial and business management related expertise. The Church through its leaders and other business partners have the mandate to make sure that people are taught and understand best business ethics and practices all the time. For example, both men and women are taught about profit maximisation; investment methods and business diversification skills. In accomplishing this, both congregants and non-congregants are constantly reminded to fear God and put him first. Given the benefits of savings and investment, one of the respondents indicated that;

In making sure that members of the church are well equipped with the best financial management skills of savings and investment, the church frequently conduct talents and tin-banking seminars and workshops to continuously reach-out the participants. During these seminars, members are taught on how best to keep their finances as well as to overcome other business related problems and risks. Though women are taught on how best they can manage their profits, they (women) are however, reminded to do this realising the importance of their husbands in the financial management process.

The above indication shows the awful extend to which both women and men are ear-marked for socio-economic empowerment and development. The response above clearly shows that gender as an academic and social discipline, is now fully acknowledged as a broad-spectrum process which is not discriminatory whatsoever based on sexuality as before. Further to note also is, it appears as if the facet of gender has now become manifold and knowledgeable to the extent that society is now recognising that family and societal businesses should be understood as a public good, which means that gender itself is now being comprehended and extended as a integrative phenomenon without any intentional sexual exclusion or inclusion. Such a set-up of events in this church, it is unquestionable that there are varied benefits of including both men and women in development processes and procedures whether in private or public spectrum. Taking into consideration the

positive paradises put in place by ZAOGA FIF, it is arguable to maintain that the Church is not restricted to its core duties of spreading the word of salvation but it is also embellishing international efforts to extinguish poverty and guarantee gender equality as enshrined in SDG 5. Nationally, the church through its leadership has proved to be complimenting the government efforts of economically empowering its diverse citizens. The government policy frameworks seeks to achieve this through the implementation of various interventions such as Zimbabwe Agenda for Sustainable Socio-Economic Transformation (ZIM ASSET).

The African Christian Business Fellowship as an Economic Empowerment tool

The African Christian Business Fellowship is a church launched establishment that brings people together who are already entrenched in the business consortium and some who endeavor to start theirs. Educating individuals; training and capacitating them to start their own businesses at zero cost is the core business of the ACBF. Even though the ACBF has no explicit funding to gratify for those aspiring to start their businesses, it was alluded that it can still link-up people to those already established for a business mentorship and experience. Deliberating on its allegiance on non-segregation on religious and sexual grounds, the African Christian Business Fellowship renders business services to everyone irregardless of being a congregant or not. The ACBF also go an extra mile monitoring the progress of your business and always give advice. It was reported that;

The African Christian Business Fellowship has exceptionally contributed towards the socio-economic empowerment of women and are better placed economically which was a hallucination especially during the historical era. Whilst men are involved in such skills development platforms, the embroilment of women on such a noticeable position indicates that women are now being acknowledged and there is more trust and belief in the competences of women in the gender terrain discourse.

In line with the sentiments above, it is undeniable that the Church is essential in spearheading economic empowerment drive for its congregants and people of Zimbabwe at large. Assuredly, in self-satisfaction of the African Christian Business Fellowship aims and goals, men are meaningfully involved through helping women with skills development. Such accomplishments mirror the gender dynamism in the church and country at large. These transformations in gender equality and women economic empowerment characterises a major positive development especially considering rareness of employment opportunities in Zimbabwe. Also, given the gender inequalities that portrayed Zimbabwean patriarchal society in terms of access and ownership of resources, women usually found themselves as a grouping with less economic ownership and control of resources. Despite all the above, it is evident that ZAOGA FIF as one of the Faith Based Institutions should be appraised for the installation of gender inequality and women disempowerment free communities in most parts of the country through its teachings and practices.

ZAOGA FIF'S Adherence to international conventions; regional and Zimbabwe's gender policy

The research established that doctrine; practices and teachings of ZAOGA FIF indicated much relevance to the prescriptions of the conventions and regional protocols signed by the Zimbabwean government. A lot of international conventions and regional protocols were put in place to address gender inequality and women disempowerment in various life facets. ZAOGA FIF positively embraced these through their biblical teachings that irregardless of sex, everyone is equal before the Lord hence life opportunities and other provisions must be shared equally. The teachings and practices within ZAOGA FIF have dissected the African patriarchal system where women were just seen as subordinates and whose human rights limited in both private and public spectrum. Through these teachings in this church, women like men are allowed to preach the word of God; women are allowed to occupy high office of authority be it in the church or society; women are ordained as leaders in the church and perform same duties like their male counter-parts.

With this action of encompassing language and elucidation of the biblical passages, many pupils in ZAOGA FIF and society at large become aware that the scriptures cannot be accustomed as a tool to condone evil or discriminate anyone due to gender set up. Christ's salvation as well as scriptural texts is inclusive and not exclusive to any gender, race, people or language. Such knowledge and understanding of the scriptures by ZAOGA FIF founder and entire leadership has immensely contributed to gender parity and spearhead sustainable development in the church and all spectrums in Zimbabwe. The church is continually improving its homiletics teachings and practices that every human person, man or woman should be equally recognised, respected and appreciated as people created in the image and likeness of God. With these teachings and practices, it clearly shows that ZAOGA FIF has embraced the alcove or niche by the Zimbabwe's national gender policy of 2022, which calls for equitable distribution of resources among its citizens and economic empowerment irregardless of sex. Zimbabwe, through its gender policy, acknowledges that women's economic empowerment is key to the country's socio-economic growth, hence the ZAOGA FIF through its teachings; practices and programmes is on track in bringing that idea into reality.

Conclusion

Although it is not conceivable to run through all issues pertaining to Gender Equality and Women Economic Empowerment done by Faith Based Institutions, this article has substantially accentuated that the church in question has cherished gender equality and socio-economic empowerment of women through engaging a number of interventions and means. The teachings and practices emanated from ZAOGA FIF founder and leadership have managed to bury the predominant male ideology which has ensured that women endure to be clients in the churches just as they were in shrines of traditional society. The church, (ZAOGA FIF) had opened up new

opportunities for women through education for girls and through authoritative leadership positions occupied by women. The strategies employed by church through their practices and teachings conform to several international conventions; regional protocols and constitutional legal provisions that call for furtherance of gender parity and women socio-economic empowerment in all spheres of life. Both women and men are treated equally; both are allowed to occupy high authoritative positions based on capabilities not sex; women can freely preach the Word of God all over and are accorded leadership posts same as men. As one of the strategies, men and women are taught to use their own hands and Godly wisdom for them to seal through economic hardships. To that note, congregants or followers are always admonished that accession is a break-through which can come from minute business ventures such as selling of small items like sweets; chocolates and freezits among others. Albeit the socio-economic empowerment interventions were initially targeted at women, men are also assimilated and taught varying continuance strategies and skills. These business or entrepreneurship skills lessons are conducted through seminars and workshops at Provincial level, where women and men, young boys and girls are all accorded opportunity to attend. It was emphasised that both youths and Sunday school kids are empowered from an early stage through participating in tin-banking system and fresh produce activities. For that reason, it is distinct that ZAOGA FIF has not only transfigured the socio-economic status of women, but it has also commenced maintainable or supportable gender alliances amongst men and women at both family and outside levels. Such is the situation, especially envisaging the fact that, in the ancient times of the ZAOGA FIF church, the focus on socio-economic empowerment was mainly targeting women who were more vulnerable to marginalisation dilemmas and most of them were not working.

On a progressive note, the church now employed a multi-pronged strategy to shelter both men and women after a realisation that the economic catastrophes were not sexually defined in the church and entire communities at large. Evidently, such tramps confirm how the church as an institution has dismantled gender predilections related with discriminatory developmental approaches. These changes signify true impression of how the society, through the abetment of Faith Based Institutions, has logically transformed itself in mainstreaming gendered development approach in all facets of life.

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